

Bitcoin Mnemonic Backup via Threshold XOR (n -of- m)

A pen-and-paper adaptation of the Kurihara scheme to BIP39

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Abstract

Backing up a BIP39 mnemonic forces a trade-off between the fragility of a single copy and the operational complexity of multisig or software-based threshold schemes (Shamir, SLIP-39, Codex32), the latter relying on finite-field arithmetic. We adapt the ideal threshold XOR secret-sharing scheme of Kurihara, Kiyomoto, Fukushima and Tanaka (2008) to BIP39 mnemonics, yielding an n -of- m pen-and-paper backup in which every operation — generation and reconstruction — reduces to XORs of hexadecimal strings, with no modular arithmetic, no finite field, and no mandatory software. Any n of the m shares reconstruct the seed, while strictly fewer than n reveal nothing (perfect, information-theoretic confidentiality up to the threshold). Each share is exactly the size of the secret and re-encodes to a valid BIP39 mnemonic, providing plausible deniability. We share only the entropy and let the BIP39 checksum act as a safeguard; we give concrete parameters for 12- and 24-word mnemonics (2-of-3 and 3-of-5), detail the reconstruction by Gaussian elimination over GF(2) including the regeneration of a lost share, restate the scheme's two security theorems with explicit verifications for the central configuration, and provide ready-to-print templates and a reference implementation.

Keywords: secret sharing; threshold scheme; XOR; BIP39; Bitcoin; mnemonic backup; information-theoretic security; plausible deniability.

1 Introduction

Backing up a BIP39 mnemonic is a balancing act. A single copy, on paper or metal, is simple but fragile: a fire, a theft, a water leak, and the private key is gone. At the other extreme, multisig offers robustness and recovery but multiplies the number of keys to operate and complicates everyday use. In between lie the threshold schemes — Shamir, SLIP-39, Codex32 — elegant and well battle-tested, but which rely on finite-field arithmetic and therefore, in practice, on software to generate and reconstruct the shares.

There is a pen-and-paper alternative: SeedXOR, from Coldcard. You split the seed into m pieces linked by XOR, and all m are needed to reconstruct it. Its major flaw is the absence of loss tolerance: if any one of the m pieces disappears, everything is lost.

This document proposes a middle path: an n -of- m threshold scheme in which any gathering of n shares out of m suffices to reconstruct the seed, in which strictly fewer than n shares reveals nothing, and in which all operations — generation as well as reconstruction

— are carried out with XORs of hexadecimal strings. No modular arithmetic by hand, no finite field, no mandatory software. The underlying scheme is that of Kurihara, Kiyomoto, Fukushima and Tanaka (2008) [1]. My contribution is to adapt it specifically to BIP39: I detail how to share the entropy and let the checksum act as a safeguard, propose concrete parameters for 12 and 24 words, and provide ready-to-print paper templates.

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2 What a BIP39 mnemonic actually shares

A 24-word BIP39 mnemonic is not 24 independent words. Each word encodes 11 bits of information, for 264 bits in total: 256 bits of randomly drawn entropy, plus 8 checksum bits defined as the first 8 bits of the SHA-256 of that entropy. For 12 words, the breakdown is analogous: 128 bits of entropy, 4 bits of checksum. The optional passphrase is not part of the mnemonic in the BIP39 sense; it is combined with the seed later, during key derivation. Its use is left to the operator and is outside the scope of this paper.

From this structure, three principles guide the backup.

First, we share only the entropy. The 256 bits suffice to rebuild the words: the checksum is recomputed. Including the checksum in the shares would, moreover, make plausible deniability of the shares impossible. Each share is exactly L bits, the size of a standard BIP39 entropy; it can therefore be re-encoded as is into a decoy mnemonic, distinct from the true secret, whose checksum is recomputed from its *own* bits and which thus passes all BIP39 checks. It is this property that makes an isolated share indistinguishable from an ordinary wallet. Embedding the original secret's checksum on top of that would break the illusion: the share re-encoded into 24 words would then carry a checksum that no longer matches the SHA-256 of its own bits, and an adversary testing it would see an invalid BIP39 mnemonic — an unambiguous signal that they are dealing with a manipulated fragment, not a wallet.

Second, the checksum is a safeguard. After rebuilding the entropy from the fragments, we re-encode it into words and check that the checksum bits carried by the final words come out right. If they do not, a transcription error has crept in somewhere. We will not always know which one, but we will know there is one: the mnemonic will then simply be rejected by any BIP39-compliant wallet, and there is no risk of using it inadvertently.

Third, the reconstructed mnemonic is ephemeral. We regenerate it from the shares when we need it, import it into the hardware wallet, and destroy it immediately. The shares alone constitute the persistent storage of the secret; the mnemonic is merely a temporary representation between the shares and the wallet, and must never survive on paper, on screen, or on any other medium.

Throughout the rest of this paper, L denotes the length in bits of the shared entropy, $L \in \{128, 256\}$.

3 Building the sharing

The general formula of the scheme,

$$W_{i,q} = \bigoplus_{t=0}^{n-2} R_{(t \cdot i + q) \bmod p}^{(t)} \oplus K_{(q-i) \bmod p},$$

may look opaque on first reading. We will arrive at it incrementally: each ingredient will be introduced when a concrete case makes it necessary.

3.1 The starting point: 2-of-2

The simplest case is the split into two shares both of which are needed to reconstruct the secret — exactly SeedXOR. We draw a random value R of the same length as the secret s , then set

$$S_0 = R, \quad S_1 = s \oplus R.$$

Reconstruction is immediate: $S_0 \oplus S_1 = R \oplus s \oplus R = s$. So is confidentiality: as long as we see only a single share, we see either pure randomness (S_0), or the secret masked by a random value we do not know (S_1). In either case, no information about s .

The limitation is just as immediate: if either of the two shares disappears, everything is lost. This is precisely the loss tolerance that the following sections will add.

3.2 2-of-3: the idea of cyclic rotation

We now want three shares any two of which suffice. A single share must say nothing; any two shares, whichever they are, must say everything.

The idea is to split the secret into several fragments, mask them with random values, then *rotate* the fragments from one share to the next. With m shares, we split s into $m - 1$ fragments of $L/(m - 1)$ bits each. For our case $m = 3$, this gives two halves K_1 and K_2 of $L/2$ bits. We draw three random values R_0, R_1, R_2 of $L/2$ bits each. Each share contains two pieces, and the position of each fragment in the share depends on the index of the share:

$$\begin{aligned} S_0 : & \quad R_0, & \quad R_1 \oplus K_1 \\ S_1 : & \quad R_0 \oplus K_2, & \quad R_1 \\ S_2 : & \quad R_0 \oplus K_1, & \quad R_1 \oplus K_2 \end{aligned}$$

This pattern can be written in a single formula if we adopt the convention $K_0 = 0$ (the “null” fragment). The piece at position q of share i is then

$$W_{i,q} = R_q \oplus K_{(q-i) \bmod 3}.$$

For $i = 0$, the fragments appear in their natural order: position 0 carries $K_0 = 0$, position 1 carries K_1 . For $i = 1$, the order is shifted by one notch: position 0 carries $K_{-1 \bmod 3} = K_2$, position 1 carries $K_0 = 0$. For $i = 2$, a shift of two notches. It is this cyclic rotation of the fragments that lets two shares complement one another.

Let us check on the coalition $\{S_0, S_1\}$. XORing the pieces at the same position,

$$W_{0,0} \oplus W_{1,0} = R_0 \oplus (R_0 \oplus K_2) = K_2,$$

$$W_{0,1} \oplus W_{1,1} = (R_1 \oplus K_1) \oplus R_1 = K_1.$$

The random value R_q cancels because it appears exactly twice in the XOR — an even number, hence zero — and only the fragments remain. The coalition $\{S_0, S_2\}$ directly yields K_1 and the combination $K_1 \oplus K_2$, from which K_2 follows. The coalition $\{S_1, S_2\}$ proceeds symmetrically. In every case, $s = K_1 \parallel K_2$.

On the confidentiality side, an isolated share holds two pieces each masked by a random value that no one else sees. The fragments remain uniformly distributed from the observer’s point of view.

We already have half the general formula: the cyclic rotation $K_{(q-i) \bmod p}$ and a first set of randomness indexed simply by q . It remains to understand what happens for larger thresholds, and why a single randomness set will become insufficient.

3.3 Why p must be prime

A detour before raising the threshold. In the 2-of-3 case, we rotated the fragments *modulo 3*. Three shares, modulo 3, no surprise. If we want four shares, can we simply take “modulo 4”? Answer: no, and it is surprisingly visual.

The trick of the star drawn in a single stroke. Picture p points arranged in a circle, numbered 0 to $p-1$. You start from point 0 and always jump the same number of steps t : $0 \rightarrow t \rightarrow 2t \rightarrow \dots$ (modulo p). Will you visit *every* point before returning to the start?

Figure 1: The “round of jumps”. On the left, $p = 5$ prime: whatever the step, we visit all 5 points before returning to the start (here the 5-pointed star drawn in a single stroke). On the right, $p = 4$ non-prime: jumping by 2s oscillates between 0 and 2 and completely misses the odd positions (dashed). This is exactly the collision that will break security in our scheme.

If p is *prime*, yes — always, whatever t . This is what lets a child draw a 5- or 7-pointed star without lifting the pencil. If p is *not* prime, it depends: for steps that share a divisor with p , you quickly retrace your steps. On 4 points, jumping by 2s oscillates between 0 and 2 (Figure 1); on 6 points, jumping by 2s only draws a triangle.

Why this picture describes our problem. For randomness set t (we will have several once $n \geq 3$), share S_i uses a “window” of $p-1$ consecutive positions on the circle of p indices, whose starting point is shifted by $t \cdot i$ relative to S_0 . As i runs through $0, 1, \dots, m-1$, these shifts trace out exactly the trajectory of the jumps of step t . For security, the m windows must all be distinct — so the first m jumps must be distinct — so p must be prime.

The counter-example ($p = 4, t = 2$). On the round of 4 people, jumping by 2s gives $0, 2, 0, 2, \dots$: only two landings. The windows of S_0 and S_2 become identical in set $t = 2$, and XORing $W_{0,q} \oplus W_{2,q}$ cancels both randomness sets at once. Two shares recover combinations of fragments where the intended threshold was three. Leak, threshold broken.

The remedy. We choose p prime with $p \geq m$. For $m = 4$ we take $p = 5$ and generate five shares, of which only four are used. For $m \in \{3, 5\}$, $p = m$; for $m \in \{6, 7\}$, $p = 7$; and so on.

In one sentence. The primality of p guarantees that the “round of jumps” visits every point for any step t — and hence that the m shares always have distinct windows.

3.4 3-of-5: why a second randomness set

Let us return to the case we really care about: five shares any three of which suffice. Parameters: $m = 5$, $n = 3$, $p = 5$. We split s into four fragments K_1, K_2, K_3, K_4 of $L/4$ bits, plus $K_0 = 0$ by convention.

Let us first try to reuse the 2-of-3 formula with a single randomness set:

$$W_{i,q} \stackrel{?}{=} R_q \oplus K_{(q-i) \bmod 5}.$$

What does an adversary with two shares, say $\{S_0, S_1\}$, see? Exactly as in 2-of-3, XORing position by position cancels R_q and yields combinations of fragments. Two shares suffice to reconstruct the secret — whereas the intended threshold is three. The goal is not met.

What is missing is a second mask, sufficiently independent of the first that the two observed shares cannot cancel both simultaneously. So let us introduce a second randomness set $R_0^{(1)}, \dots, R_4^{(1)}$ and first try the trivial indexing:

$$W_{i,q} \stackrel{?}{=} R_q^{(0)} \oplus R_q^{(1)} \oplus K_{(q-i) \bmod 5}.$$

Still a miss: the second set behaves exactly like the first from the index point of view, and XORing two shares cancels both at once. The second mask must *rotate differently* from one share to the next. We shift it by an increment that depends on i :

$$W_{i,q} = R_q^{(0)} \oplus R_{(i+q) \bmod 5}^{(1)} \oplus K_{(q-i) \bmod 5}.$$

This time, when we XOR $W_{0,q} \oplus W_{1,q}$, the first set cancels as before, but the second yields $R_q^{(1)} \oplus R_{q+1}^{(1)}$: an unknown random value that keeps masking the combination of fragments. Two shares learn nothing.

This idea generalizes effortlessly. For an arbitrary threshold n , we need $n-1$ randomness sets, each indexed with a different “rotation speed”, naturally written as $t \cdot i$ for $t = 0, 1, \dots, n-2$:

$$W_{i,q} = \bigoplus_{t=0}^{n-2} R_{(t \cdot i + q) \bmod p}^{(t)} \oplus K_{(q-i) \bmod p}.$$

The set $t = 0$ does not depend on i and plays the role of the common mask, as in 2-of-3. The set $t = 1$ rotates at speed one. The set $t = 2$ would rotate at speed two for $n = 4$. And so on. Because p is prime, each multiplication by $t \neq 0$ is a bijection and no pair of shares ends up sharing all randomness indices simultaneously: for any coalition of fewer than n shares, at least one random value remains out of reach.

3.5 Parameter summary

The protocol is now fully specified. To share an L -bit secret into m shares with threshold n , we set p equal to the smallest prime greater than or equal to m , and $d = L/(p - 1)$ for the size of each fragment. We split the secret into $p - 1$ fragments K_1, \dots, K_{p-1} of d bits, with $K_0 = 0^d$. We draw $(n - 1) \times p$ independent, uniform random values, $R_\ell^{(t)}$ for $t \in \{0, \dots, n - 2\}$ and $\ell \in \{0, \dots, p - 1\}$. Each share S_i , for $i \in \{0, \dots, m - 1\}$, contains $p - 1$ pieces $W_{i,q}$ for $q \in \{0, \dots, p - 2\}$, computed by the general formula above. Each share is $(p - 1) \times d = L$ bits: exactly the same size as the secret.

Two profiles cover most use cases. For an individual backup, 2-of-3 with $L = 128$ bits (12 BIP39 words): three sheets of 32 hexadecimal characters, two to gather. For a team or extended-family backup, 3-of-5 with $L = 256$ bits (24 BIP39 words): five sheets of 64 hexadecimal characters, three to gather. Larger configurations remain possible (4-of-7, 5-of-9), at the cost of a bulkier derivation at each reconstruction.

4 Reconstruction by progressive elimination of the random values

Gathering n shares gives access to $n \times (p - 1)$ pieces, each a linear equation in the fragments K_q and the random values $R_\ell^{(t)}$. All the work of reconstruction consists in combining these equations by XOR so that the random values cancel out in pairs, leaving only the fragments. The combination to use is entirely determined by the parameters (n, m, p) and the chosen coalition: it can be re-derived at any time, from the parameters alone, by Gaussian elimination over $\text{GF}(2)$. For the convenience of a pen-and-paper reconstruction, we often choose to pre-compute these formulas at generation time and print them as a *recovery table*, one per coalition — but nothing requires this: an operator who knows the construction can reconstruct everything from scratch.

4.1 The 2-of-3 case

For $n = 2$, each piece $W_{i,q}$ contains a single random value, R_q , which does not depend on i . Cancelling it is direct: it suffices to XOR two pieces at the same position q belonging to two distinct shares. The random value then appears twice and vanishes, leaving a combination of fragments.

For the coalition $\{S_0, S_1\}$, the two XORs immediately give K_2 and K_1 . For $\{S_0, S_2\}$, we obtain K_1 at position 0 and $K_1 \oplus K_2$ at position 1; we isolate K_2 with one extra XOR. For $\{S_1, S_2\}$, symmetrically. In all three cases, two to three XORs of hexadecimal strings suffice to reconstruct the two fragments, and concatenation then gives the 128 bits of entropy.

4.2 The 3-of-5 case

With $n = 3$, each piece carries two random values, one from $R^{(0)}$ and one from $R^{(1)}$, at indices that depend on i and q . Cancelling a single random value no longer suffices: every index encountered in the combination must appear an even number of times, for both sets at once. This forces us to combine more than two pieces.

For the coalition $\{S_0, S_1, S_2\}$, the index table of the random values and the fragments, computed from the formula $W_{i,q} = R_q^{(0)} \oplus R_{(i+q) \bmod 5}^{(1)} \oplus K_{(q-i) \bmod 5}$, is as follows:

i	$R^{(0)}$ index				$R^{(1)}$ index				K index			
	$q=0$	$q=1$	$q=2$	$q=3$	$q=0$	$q=1$	$q=2$	$q=3$	$q=0$	$q=1$	$q=2$	$q=3$
0	0	1	2	3	0	1	2	3	0	1	2	3
1	0	1	2	3	1	2	3	4	4	0	1	2
2	0	1	2	3	2	3	4	0	3	4	0	1

This counting of index parities is exactly the solving of a linear system over $\text{GF}(2)$. We treat each of the $n(p-1) = 12$ pieces $W_{i,q}$ as an equation in $(n-1) \cdot p + (p-1) = 14$ unknowns: the ten random values $R_\ell^{(t)}$ and the four fragments K_q . We row-reduce the system by Gaussian elimination, pivoting first on the randomness columns; the final rows on which only a single fragment K_q remains on the left yield the reconstruction formulas. The computation, carried out step by step in Appendix B.4, gives for the coalition $\{S_0, S_1, S_2\}$:

$$K_1 = W_{1,0} \oplus W_{2,0} \oplus W_{0,1} \oplus W_{2,1} \oplus W_{0,2} \oplus W_{2,2} \oplus W_{0,3} \oplus W_{1,3}.$$

This can be checked by hand by reading the table above, piece by piece, in the formula for K_1 . The $R^{(0)}$ indices encountered are, in order, 0, 0, 1, 1, 2, 2, 3, 3: each value from 0 to 3 appears exactly twice, hence cancels. The $R^{(1)}$ indices are 1, 2, 1, 3, 2, 4, 3, 4: each value from 1 to 4 appears exactly twice, index 0 does not appear at all, so everything cancels too. The K indices are 4, 3, 1, 4, 2, 0, 3, 2: index 1 appears once, indices 2, 3, 4 each appear twice and cancel, index 0 appears once but $K_0 = 0$ by convention. What remains is therefore K_1 , the fragment sought.

Analogous formulas give K_2, K_3, K_4 , and the entropy is obtained by concatenation. Each of the ten possible coalitions of three shares out of five is handled by the same method — the indices change, but the mechanics are strictly identical; the detailed derivation for $\{S_0, S_1, S_2\}$ is found in Appendix B.4.

4.3 Back to BIP39

Once $s = K_1 \| K_2 \| \dots \| K_{p-1}$ has been recomposed, it remains to convert these L bits of entropy into BIP39 words: 24 words for $L = 256$, 12 words for $L = 128$. The procedure is standard: we compute the checksum — the first 8 bits of the SHA-256 of the entropy for $L = 256$, or 4 bits for $L = 128$ —, append it to the entropy bits, and split the resulting 264 (resp. 132) bits into 11-bit blocks that index the words in the BIP39 list.

What the checksum catches. This last step, if done by hand, is one of the riskiest in the whole chain: picking the wrong word in the list, reading an 11-bit block crooked, or transposing two hexadecimal digits. The checksum then plays its role as a safeguard: any BIP39-compliant wallet, when importing the mnemonic, recomputes the checksum from the first 256 bits and compares it to the 8 bits carried by the last word. If they differ, the mnemonic is rejected and the error is known before any use. The probability that a conversion error produces, *by chance*, a mnemonic with a valid checksum is 2^{-8} (or 2^{-4}) — small, but not zero.

What it does not catch. The checksum does not detect errors made *upstream* of the conversion: a mis-transcribed piece, a botched XOR, a hexadecimal digit confused during Gaussian elimination. A wrongly reconstructed entropy generates an equally internally-consistent checksum, and the resulting mnemonic will pass the BIP39 checks without complaint — it will simply correspond to *another wallet*, empty or unknown. To guard against this kind of error, it is the parity and CRC checks discussed in Section 5.2.1 that do the work, catching errors as close to their source as possible: on the pieces and the intermediate XORs, before they propagate all the way to the reconstructed entropy.

4.4 Reconstructing a lost share

If a share is damaged or misplaced, it can be reconstituted identically from any n shares chosen among the $m - 1$ remaining ones. The computation is more demanding than reconstructing the secret alone — it requires solving a linear system that includes the random values $R_\ell^{(t)}$ in addition to the fragments K_q — and is not reasonably done with pencil and paper, but the reference implementation `xor_kurihara.py` handles it. The regenerated share is bit-for-bit identical to the original and can replace the lost one without modifying the other shares in circulation. The full procedure is detailed in Appendix B.5.

This regeneration assumes, however, that the share was genuinely *lost* (paper destroyed, custodian unreachable) and not *compromised*: if one suspects that a third party has seen it, regenerating it identically leaves that third party in possession of a valid share. In that case the whole scheme must be rotated — generate a new set of random values, recompute all shares, distribute the new ones, destroy the old ones.

5 Security of the scheme and best practices

This section separates what is *proven* from what is *advised*. Section 5.1 states the two fundamental cryptographic properties of the Kurihara scheme, proven formally in Appendix B. Section 5.2 discusses the operational protections that are not part of the cryptographic scheme *stricto sensu*: integrity against errors, defence against an active adversary, surrounding assumptions. These considerations belong to implementation, and it is honest to present them for what they are — best practices, not proofs.

5.1 Proven cryptographic properties

Two strong results, proven by Kurihara et al. [1], ground the security of the scheme. They hold for any coalition of shares and for any chosen secret: no exception, no grey area.

5.1.1 Perfect confidentiality up to $n - 1$ shares

The first result is that an adversary who gathers *strictly fewer* than n shares learns **nothing** about the secret. Not “almost nothing”, not “nothing useful in practice”: nothing at all. To them, the secret remains exactly as unpredictable as before they laid hands on a single share.

Formally (Kurihara’s Theorem 1): for any coalition A of at most $n - 1$ shares, the conditional entropy of the secret given the shares of A is $H(S | V_A) = H(S)$: the conditional distribution of the secret is uniform, identical to that of an observer holding no share at all.

The intuition rests on the *sentinel* argument. For any coalition of fewer than n shares, there always exists at least one random value $R_\rho^{(t)}$ that the adversary cannot eliminate by any XOR combination of their pieces. This value, completely random and unknown to them, stays attached to a piece of a fragment; whatever they do, that piece stays masked.

Why such a sentinel always exists. We return to the image of the round of jumps (Section 3.4). For randomness set t , each share S_i uses a window of $p - 1$ consecutive indices on the circle of p positions; it therefore “misses” exactly one index. Because p is prime, these missed indices are *all distinct* from one share to the next.

For the central case of this paper, 3-of-5 with two adversarial shares, take $A = \{S_0, S_1\}$. For the set $t = 1$, the share S_0 uses the indices $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ and misses index 4; the share S_1 uses $\{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ and misses index 0. Index $\ell = 0$ thus appears only once in the whole coalition (in the piece $W_{0,0}$), and index $\ell = 4$ only once (in $W_{1,3}$). There are our two sentinels: no XOR combination can cancel them, and the piece of secret they cover stays random for the adversary. The argument generalizes to any coalition A of fewer than n shares; the clean algebraic proof (full rank of the coalition matrix) is in Appendix B.

5.1.2 Recoverability of the secret from n shares

The second result says that as soon as n shares are gathered, the secret is uniquely determined by the observed pieces: there exists only one $s = K_1 \parallel \dots \parallel K_{p-1}$ compatible with what is seen. Formally (Kurihara’s Theorem 2): for any coalition A of at least n shares, $H(S \mid V_A) = 0$.

This is what makes the scheme usable in practice: there is no doubt during reconstruction, no several candidates to disambiguate. Section 4 showed the mechanics step by step (Gaussian elimination on the pieces and the random values, then reading off the fragments); the formal uniqueness proof appears in Appendix B.

Combined. The two theorems mean that the transition between “secret perfectly hidden” and “secret fully accessible” is *binary*: strictly fewer than n shares \Rightarrow perfect confidentiality; exactly n shares or more \Rightarrow unique secret. No grey area, no progressive leak as the number of shares grows. This is the central property that characterizes a perfect threshold secret-sharing scheme in the information-theoretic sense.

5.2 Practical considerations beyond the formal framework

The theorems above assume a *passive* adversary (who observes without modifying) and an *ideal* environment (perfectly uniform randomness, secure physical media, error-free transcription). None of these assumptions comes for free in practice. The paragraphs that follow list the gaps between model and reality, and the corresponding mitigations. None is covered by the proofs of Section 5.1: these are best practices.

5.2.1 Integrity against accidental errors

XOR alone detects no error. A skipped line, a misread hexadecimal digit, and reconstruction silently produces a wrong entropy — which is then encoded into BIP39 words without complaint (the checksum recomputes correctly from that wrong entropy, see Section 4.3). The wallet will import the mnemonic, which will simply correspond to *another* wallet,

empty or unknown. For a manual backup that one may use only once in a lifetime, that is unacceptable.

We therefore add two layers of control to the transcription. First, a local per-line parity: the XOR of all the hexadecimal digits of the line, written in the margin, detects a one-character transcription error on the line. Second, a CRC-8 or CRC-16 per page, computed once at generation time and recorded on the sheet, provides a more robust global check. These checks do not correct errors: they flag them. In case of a discrepancy, one goes back to the originals or to a neighbouring share to reconstruct.

5.2.2 Active adversary

An *active* adversary — a dishonest custodian, a targeted burglar, a compromised courier — could intentionally modify one or more shares *after their distribution* to make a future reconstruction yield a wrong entropy. Note that such an attacker gains nothing in terms of theft: reconstructing the secret requires n shares, and if they had them, they would decrypt them directly rather than sabotage them. Their motivation is therefore pure sabotage — harming the legitimate owner by leading them to reconstruct an empty wallet that they will believe is theirs. This risk is marginal for domestic use, where it would require a relative to be both a custodian and actively malicious. It becomes relevant, however, in an institutional environment: contested inheritance, competing custodians, governance conflicts, a leaking employee.

The CRC does not defend against this scenario: the attacker can recompute the CRC of the share they modified. Two complementary approaches:

- **Publish a separate MAC.** We compute the SHA-256 of the entropy at generation time and store this hash outside the shares (a piece of paper in an independent safe, for instance). At reconstruction, we recompute the SHA-256 on the reconstructed entropy and compare. Any alteration of a share then shows up as a hash that does not match, and we know we are holding a wrong version before any use. This is the real defence against sabotage.
- **Independent double entry.** Two operators transcribe the shares separately and compare their reconstructions. This protection targets transcription errors, not alterations of the share itself: if the sheet is already falsified, both operators will read the same corrupted version and reconstruct the same wrong entropy. It is therefore complementary to the MAC, not an alternative.

For domestic use, these protections are generally disproportionate. For institutional use, the separate MAC is a baseline best practice.

5.2.3 What the scheme does not cover

The cryptographic security of the scheme assumes that the $(n - 1) \times p$ random values are drawn uniformly and independently, and that they are generated offline on an uncompromised machine. Weak or correlated randomness — loaded dice, a predictable RNG, poor system entropy — compromises the whole edifice.

It also assumes that the BIP39 mnemonic, once reconstituted, is never stored durably. This is the normal way to use a seed: import it into the hardware wallet, confirm everything works, then immediately destroy the reconstructed copy. The shares remain the sole persistent storage of the secret; the reconstructed mnemonic is merely a transient state between the shares and the wallet, and must never linger on paper, on screen, or on any other medium.

Finally, the scheme says nothing about the physical security of the media: safes, sealed envelopes, distinct locations, periodic rotation. These considerations, classic for any paper backup, are the subject of the next section.

6 Practical implementation

6.1 Parameter choice

The pair (n, m) and the size L depend on the threat profile and the number of trusted custodians. For an individual or couple's backup, 2-of-3 with $L = 128$ tolerates the loss of one share and keeps the threshold low: two people or two locations suffice to reconstruct. For a team or extended-family configuration, 3-of-5 with $L = 256$ offers more robustness (two losses tolerated) and a higher threshold against collusion. Larger configurations (4-of-7, 5-of-9) are possible but make the derivation at each reconstruction, and the governance, heavier; I recommend staying with the base profiles unless there is an explicit need.

6.2 Offline generation

Generation must be done on an air-gapped machine, ideally booted from a clean live USB with no network access for the entire session. The entropy s comes from the mnemonic to be backed up, either by retyping it or by deriving it from the words via a standard BIP39 routine. The random values $R_\ell^{(t)}$ must be drawn from a verified source: physical dice, coin tosses, or failing that `/dev/urandom` on the offline machine. A reference implementation, `xor_kurihara.py`, accompanies this document and handles the XOR computations from user-supplied randomness; it does not generate the randomness itself, precisely to leave the operator the choice of source.

The pieces $W_{i,q}$ are computed, then transcribed onto the share sheets with parities and CRC, then the machine is switched off and the ephemeral media (RAM, temporary files) wiped. Ideally, the entire session leaves no digital trace: only the paper sheets remain.

6.3 Distribution, governance, rotation

Each share, once transcribed, is placed in a sealed envelope and entrusted to a distinct custodian — a trusted physical person or an independent location: a bank vault, a parent's home, a notary. The locations must be geographically separated: not two shares in the same house, nor in the same town if possible. A local disaster (fire, flood, burglary) must carry off at most one share.

An annual audit consists in verifying, without reconstructing the secret, that each share still exists, that the sheet is legible, and that the CRCs come out right. This check detects silent degradation — fading ink, humidity, a forgotten custodian — before it makes reconstruction impossible.

Periodic rotation consists in regenerating a new instance of the scheme with new random values, distributing the new shares, and physically destroying the old ones after confirming that the new ones work. It protects against the wear of the media as well as against a possible past partial leak. The cadence depends on the durability of the physical medium:

- **Ordinary paper:** every 2 to 3 years. Sensitive to humidity, fire, UV, and ink fading.

- **Archival or laminated paper:** every 5 to 7 years. Resistant to everyday humidity, but the ink remains vulnerable.
- **Engraved plastic plate** (Cryptosteel-like, but in plastic): every 10 years. Resists water and UV, but plastic melts in a fire.
- **Engraved metal** (stainless steel, titanium): every 15 to 20 years, or more. Resists fire, water, UV. The annual check remains useful to confirm legibility, and rotation remains recommended to limit the cumulative exposure of a single instance.
- **Digital media** (USB stick, microSD): to be avoided for long-term use — typical lifespan of 5 to 10 years, but with a risk of silent failure (bits flipping without warning). If used anyway, annual verification is mandatory and rotation every 3 to 5 years.

Whatever the medium, the goal is not only to prevent degradation: it is also to rotate the secret to limit the impact of an undetected past leak.

7 Conclusion

The scheme presented here offers a middle path between the fragile single copy and the complex software solutions. It runs with pencil and paper, each operation — generation as well as reconstruction — reducing to XORs of hexadecimal strings. These XORs can be done directly, bit by bit or hexadecimal character by hexadecimal character; they can also be pre-computed once and for all at generation time as a recovery table, which speeds up reconstruction at the cost of a little paper. The scheme is ideal in the sense that each share weighs exactly the same number of bits as the secret, and it offers perfect confidentiality up to the threshold. Applied to BIP39, it shares the entropy alone and lets the checksum play its role as a safeguard.

The trade-off is that one must live with manual integrity checks (per-line parity, per-page CRC). It is not a tool to handle distractedly, but it remains within reach of anyone who can read a hexadecimal sheet and align two columns of digits. For many bitcoiners, that is the right compromise.

A Ready-to-print templates (3-of-5, $L = 256$)

Two template pages to photocopy and fill in by hand at generation time: the “Master” sheet that gathers all the secret ingredients (to be destroyed after distribution), and the share sheet which holds three shares per page (two photocopies suffice for the 5 custodians of a 3-of-5 instance). Each share carries its own instance metadata so as to remain identifiable even once cut out of the sheet.

A share boils down to the $L = 256$ bits of the BIP39 mnemonic: the $W_{i,q}$ are derived from it by removing the 8 checksum bits and splitting the remaining 256 bits into $p - 1 = 4$ pieces of 64 bits.

“Master” sheet — 3-of-5 instance, $L = 256$

Secret fragments (with $K_0 = 0$)

#	Value (hex, 16 chars)	Parity	Init.
K_1			
K_2			
K_3			
K_4			

Randomness — Set $R^{(0)}$

#	Value (hex, 16 chars)	Parity	Init.
$R_0^{(0)}$			
$R_1^{(0)}$			
$R_2^{(0)}$			
$R_3^{(0)}$			
$R_4^{(0)}$			

Randomness — Set $R^{(1)}$

#	Value (hex, 16 chars)	Parity	Init.
$R_0^{(1)}$			
$R_1^{(1)}$			
$R_2^{(1)}$			
$R_3^{(1)}$			
$R_4^{(1)}$			

Expected count: 14 lines (4 fragments + 10 random values).

Instance metadata

Version	Instance uuid
Parameters	$(m, n, L, p) = (5, 3, 256, 5)$	Encoding	Hex, 16 chars/piece
Date	Operators
crc-8 (page)	Notes

To be destroyed at the end of generation. This sheet gathers all the secret ingredients (fragments and random values). Once the shares have been distributed and a test reconstruction carried out successfully — gather n shares, recover the secret, check that it matches the expected mnemonic —, this sheet *must* be physically destroyed (shredding, incineration). Generation only ends with shares in circulation and no central trace of the secret.

Share sheet — 3-of-5 instance, $L = 256$

Share $S_?$ Identifier $i \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$:

BIP39 mnemonic (24 words)

1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.
7.	8.	9.	10.	11.	12.
13.	14.	15.	16.	17.	18.
19.	20.	21.	22.	23.	24.

crc-8 (page):

Version uuid

Parameters (5, 3, 256, 5) Date

Share $S_?$ Identifier $i \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$:

BIP39 mnemonic (24 words)

1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.
7.	8.	9.	10.	11.	12.
13.	14.	15.	16.	17.	18.
19.	20.	21.	22.	23.	24.

crc-8 (page):

Version uuid

Parameters (5, 3, 256, 5) Date

Share $S_?$ Identifier $i \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$:

BIP39 mnemonic (24 words)

1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.
7.	8.	9.	10.	11.	12.
13.	14.	15.	16.	17.	18.
19.	20.	21.	22.	23.	24.

crc-8 (page):

Version uuid

Parameters (5, 3, 256, 5) Date

B Proof elements and tests

This appendix formalizes the arguments sketched in the body of the text. It is designed to stay readable on its own, without systematic cross-references to the previous sections; we therefore briefly recall the notation.

Scope. The appendix *states* precisely the two Kurihara theorems, *verifies* their conclusions on the paper’s central configuration (3-of-5, coalition $\{S_0, S_1\}$ for confidentiality; coalition $\{S_0, S_1, S_2\}$ for reconstruction), and *refers* to the original article [1] for the general formal proof, which mobilizes several technical lemmas on $\text{GF}(p)$ and $\text{GF}(2^d)$. The goal here is not to reproduce these proofs in full depth, but to make verifiable, by pencil or by implementation, what is useful for using this scheme.

B.1 Linear framework over $\text{GF}(2^d)$

We recall the scheme’s formula:

$$W_{i,q} = \bigoplus_{t=0}^{n-2} R_{(t \cdot i + q) \bmod p}^{(t)} \oplus K_{(q-i) \bmod p},$$

where p is prime, $p \geq m$, $d = L/(p-1)$, the K_q are the fragments of the secret (with $K_0 = 0^d$) and the $R_\ell^{(t)}$ the random values. Each piece $W_{i,q}$ is a linear equation in the vector space $\text{GF}(2^d)$. Stacking the pieces of a coalition A of shares into a vector \vec{W}_A , the system reads

$$M_A \cdot \vec{R} \oplus N_A \cdot \vec{K} = \vec{W}_A,$$

where M_A is the matrix expressing each piece in terms of the $(n-1) \cdot p$ randomness unknowns, and N_A the one expressing it in terms of the $p-1$ unknown fragments ($K_0 = 0$ being absorbed). The system has as many equations as collected pieces — one per pair (i, q) with $S_i \in A$ and $q \in \{0, \dots, p-2\}$.

B.2 Perfect confidentiality when A has fewer than n shares

Theorem. For p prime and any coalition A of at most $n-1$ shares, the matrix M_A has full row rank.

Consequence. The image of M_A is the entire space. For any candidate secret $s' = K'_1 \parallel \dots \parallel K'_{p-1}$, there exists a randomness vector \vec{R}' such that $M_A \cdot \vec{R}' \oplus N_A \cdot \vec{K}' = \vec{W}_A$, that is, producing exactly the same observed pieces. The adversary therefore cannot distinguish the real secret from any other: the conditional distribution of the secret is uniform, and $\Pr[s = x \mid \vec{W}_A] = 2^{-L}$ for every x .

Structural argument. Full rank is equivalent to saying that no non-trivial linear combination of the rows of M_A is zero — or again, that no non-empty subset of pieces $S \subseteq \{W_{i,q} \mid S_i \in A, 0 \leq q \leq p-2\}$ XORs to an expression where all the random values have cancelled.

The argument relies on the notion of a *sentinel*: an index (t, ℓ) such that $R_\ell^{(t)}$ appears in only a single piece of the whole coalition. If such a sentinel exists, then any subset S containing that piece has its sentinel random value surviving with odd parity (impossible

to cancel), and any S excluding it is restricted to a strictly smaller subset where the argument can be repeated by induction.

For p prime and $t \neq 0$, the map $i \mapsto t \cdot i \bmod p$ is a bijection of $\mathbb{Z}/p\mathbb{Z}$ onto itself. Each share S_i therefore “misses” a different index in set t , which makes structural sentinels exist within the coalition — the general proof appears in the original article by Kurihara et al. [1]. For the configurations of this paper ($n \in \{2, 3\}$), it can be verified directly.

Verification for $n = 3$, $p = 5$, $A = \{S_0, S_1\}$. For the set $t = 1$, the share S_0 uses the indices $\{0 + q \bmod 5 \mid q = 0, \dots, 3\} = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, and the share S_1 uses $\{1 + q \bmod 5 \mid q = 0, \dots, 3\} = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$. Index $\ell = 0$ appears only in the piece $W_{0,0}$, and index $\ell = 4$ only in $W_{1,3}$: these are the sentinels. Any subset S that includes $W_{0,0}$ contains $R_0^{(1)}$ once (odd), incompatible with elimination; likewise if S includes $W_{1,3}$. If S excludes these two pieces, it can only combine pieces with $q \in \{1, 2\}$, and a direct examination shows that other odd indices then remain. No non-empty S eliminates all the random values. Full rank is confirmed.

The other nine coalitions of two shares (out of $\binom{5}{2} = 10$) are handled by the same argument up to a rotation: the construction being invariant under cyclic shift, the roles of shares S_0 and S_1 can be played by any pair (S_a, S_b) with $a \neq b$.

Additional verifications. Full rank was verified explicitly by implementation for the configurations 2-of-3 (A of one share), 3-of-5 (A of two shares) and 4-of-5 (A of three shares), by enumerating all possible coalitions. The script `xor_kurihara.py` accompanies this document and performs these verifications.

B.3 Correctness when A has n shares

Theorem. With a coalition A of exactly n shares, the secret is uniquely determined by the observed pieces.

Proof. The system has $n(p - 1)$ equations. The matrix M_A has rank $(n - 1)(p - 1)$ — that is, the *same* rank as for a coalition A of $n - 1$ shares (where it is the full row rank). In other words, the n -th share adds $(p - 1)$ equations on the randomness, but all linearly dependent on the previous ones: it is precisely this redundancy that lets the random values cancel out by XOR. The $p - 1$ columns of N_A then contribute $p - 1$ linearly independent dimensions to the combined system, which completes the rank:

$$(n - 1)(p - 1) + (p - 1) = n(p - 1) = \text{number of equations.}$$

The system therefore has a unique solution in \vec{K} . Solving it is done by Gaussian elimination over $\text{GF}(2^d)$, and that is what the detailed derivation in Appendix B.4 concretely carries out.

Note on the random values. The theorem says nothing about the $R_\ell^{(t)}$, and for good reason: they are never fully determined by the pieces, even with all m shares. A residual degree of freedom remains on the random values, a consequence of a shift symmetry — simultaneously replacing $R_\ell^{(t)} \mapsto R_\ell^{(t)} \oplus c$ for all (t, ℓ) and any c leaves each piece $W_{i,q}$ unchanged (the random values appearing in the piece’s formula are shifted by the same amount, which cancels mutually by XOR). This ambiguity is invisible to observers and

has no bearing on the reconstructed secret; it does, however, play a role in reconstructing a lost share, where it guarantees that any arbitrarily chosen value for the free variable leads to the same regenerated share (Appendix B.5).

B.4 Full reconstruction: 3-of-5, coalition $\{S_0, S_1, S_2\}$

The abstract proof above guarantees uniqueness of the solution in \vec{K} . We put it into practice on a concrete case: parameters $(n, m, p) = (3, 5, 5)$, coalition $\{S_0, S_1, S_2\}$. The other nine coalitions, as well as the other parameter sets (n, m, L) , are handled in strictly analogous fashion.

Setting up the equations. Each of the $n(p-1) = 12$ pieces $W_{i,q}$ is, by construction, a linear equation over $\text{GF}(2^d)$. Applying the formula

$$W_{i,q} = R_q^{(0)} \oplus R_{(i+q) \bmod 5}^{(1)} \oplus K_{(q-i) \bmod 5}$$

with the convention $K_0 = 0$, we expand the pieces of each share separately.

The twelve pieces, grouped by share:

Share S_0	Share S_1	Share S_2
$W_{0,0} = R_0^{(0)} \oplus R_0^{(1)},$	$W_{1,0} = R_0^{(0)} \oplus R_1^{(1)} \oplus K_4,$	$W_{2,0} = R_0^{(0)} \oplus R_2^{(1)} \oplus K_3,$
$W_{0,1} = R_1^{(0)} \oplus R_1^{(1)} \oplus K_1,$	$W_{1,1} = R_1^{(0)} \oplus R_2^{(1)},$	$W_{2,1} = R_1^{(0)} \oplus R_3^{(1)} \oplus K_4,$
$W_{0,2} = R_2^{(0)} \oplus R_2^{(1)} \oplus K_2,$	$W_{1,2} = R_2^{(0)} \oplus R_3^{(1)} \oplus K_1,$	$W_{2,2} = R_2^{(0)} \oplus R_4^{(1)},$
$W_{0,3} = R_3^{(0)} \oplus R_3^{(1)} \oplus K_3.$	$W_{1,3} = R_3^{(0)} \oplus R_4^{(1)} \oplus K_2.$	$W_{2,3} = R_3^{(0)} \oplus R_0^{(1)} \oplus K_1.$

The unknowns are the ten random values $R_0^{(0)}, \dots, R_4^{(0)}, R_0^{(1)}, \dots, R_4^{(1)}$ and the four fragments K_1, K_2, K_3, K_4 , for 14 in total. Since $R_4^{(0)}$ appears in no piece (the indices $R_q^{(0)}$ run from 0 to $p-2$), only 13 unknowns are actually active, for 12 equations: the system retains one degree of freedom in randomness, but as we will see, the fragments K_q are themselves fully determined.

First pass: eliminating the $R_q^{(0)}$ via S_0 . For fixed q , the piece $W_{0,q}$ serves as pivot for the column $R_q^{(0)}$: we XOR it into $W_{1,q}$ and into $W_{2,q}$. We obtain two families of four residual equations, which we label A_q for the residuals of S_1 and B_q for those of S_2 .

Residuals of S_1 (column A)

Residuals of S_2 (column B)

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &:= W_{0,0} \oplus W_{1,0} \\ &= R_0^{(1)} \oplus R_1^{(1)} \oplus K_4, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} B_1 &:= W_{0,0} \oplus W_{2,0} \\ &= R_0^{(1)} \oplus R_2^{(1)} \oplus K_3, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} A_2 &:= W_{0,1} \oplus W_{1,1} \\ &= R_1^{(1)} \oplus R_2^{(1)} \oplus K_1, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} B_2 &:= W_{0,1} \oplus W_{2,1} \\ &= R_1^{(1)} \oplus R_3^{(1)} \oplus K_1 \oplus K_4, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} A_3 &:= W_{0,2} \oplus W_{1,2} \\ &= R_2^{(1)} \oplus R_3^{(1)} \oplus K_1 \oplus K_2, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} B_3 &:= W_{0,2} \oplus W_{2,2} \\ &= R_2^{(1)} \oplus R_4^{(1)} \oplus K_2, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} A_4 &:= W_{0,3} \oplus W_{1,3} \\ &= R_3^{(1)} \oplus R_4^{(1)} \oplus K_2 \oplus K_3. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} B_4 &:= W_{0,3} \oplus W_{2,3} \\ &= R_0^{(1)} \oplus R_3^{(1)} \oplus K_1 \oplus K_3. \end{aligned}$$

It remains to eliminate the five random values of set $t = 1$. We will use the A_i as pivots; the B_j will purge their randomness and yield the final system in K_q .

Second pass: telescoping the $R_\ell^{(1)}$. The key observation: each A_i contains *two consecutive randomness indices*, $R_{i-1}^{(1)}$ and $R_i^{(1)}$. This is no coincidence — it is the direct consequence of the speed-1 shift chosen for set $t = 1$ in Section 3.4: the share S_i uses the indices $(i + q) \bmod p$, and $W_{0,q} \oplus W_{1,q}$ therefore links indices q and $q + 1$. A chain $A_{a+1} \oplus A_{a+2} \oplus \dots \oplus A_b$ has, on the randomness side, the telescoping sum

$$(R_a^{(1)} \oplus R_{a+1}^{(1)}) \oplus (R_{a+1}^{(1)} \oplus R_{a+2}^{(1)}) \oplus \dots \oplus (R_{b-1}^{(1)} \oplus R_b^{(1)}) = R_a^{(1)} \oplus R_b^{(1)}.$$

All the intermediate indices appear twice and cancel; only the two endpoints a and b remain. In other words, the chain $A_{a+1} \oplus \dots \oplus A_b$ behaves, on the randomness side, exactly like the pair $R_a^{(1)} \oplus R_b^{(1)}$.

Now each B_j contains precisely such a pair of indices. It therefore suffices to XOR the right “bridge” of A_i into each B_j to purge its random values. We thus obtain four equations α_j containing only K_q :

B_1 contains $R_0^{(1)} \oplus R_2^{(1)}$, we XOR the chain $A_1 \oplus A_2$:

$$\alpha_1 := B_1 \oplus A_1 \oplus A_2.$$

On the randomness side, the result is zero; on the K side, $K_3 \oplus K_4 \oplus K_1 = K_1 \oplus K_3 \oplus K_4$; on the pieces side,

$$\alpha_1 = (W_{0,0} \oplus W_{2,0}) \oplus (W_{0,0} \oplus W_{1,0}) \oplus (W_{0,1} \oplus W_{1,1}) = W_{0,1} \oplus W_{1,0} \oplus W_{1,1} \oplus W_{2,0}.$$

B_2 contains $R_1^{(1)} \oplus R_3^{(1)}$, chain $A_2 \oplus A_3$:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_2 &:= B_2 \oplus A_2 \oplus A_3 \\ &= W_{0,2} \oplus W_{1,1} \oplus W_{1,2} \oplus W_{2,1}, \\ \alpha_2 &= K_1 \oplus K_2 \oplus K_4. \end{aligned}$$

B_3 contains $R_2^{(1)} \oplus R_4^{(1)}$, chain $A_3 \oplus A_4$:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_3 &:= B_3 \oplus A_3 \oplus A_4 \\ &= W_{0,3} \oplus W_{1,2} \oplus W_{1,3} \oplus W_{2,2}, \\ \alpha_3 &= K_1 \oplus K_2 \oplus K_3. \end{aligned}$$

B_4 contains $R_0^{(1)} \oplus R_3^{(1)}$, chain $A_1 \oplus A_2 \oplus A_3$:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_4 &:= B_4 \oplus A_1 \oplus A_2 \oplus A_3 \\ &= W_{0,0} \oplus W_{0,1} \oplus W_{0,2} \oplus W_{0,3} \oplus W_{1,0} \oplus W_{1,1} \oplus W_{1,2} \oplus W_{2,3}, \\ \alpha_4 &= K_1 \oplus K_2 \oplus K_3 \oplus K_4. \end{aligned}$$

The random value $R_4^{(1)}$ appears in no equation α_j (it was never used as a variable to eliminate): it is the free variable announced above, with no bearing on the reconstruction of the K_q .

Solving the reduced system in K_q . We have four linear equations in K_1, K_2, K_3, K_4 :

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_1 &= K_1 \oplus K_3 \oplus K_4, & \alpha_3 &= K_1 \oplus K_2 \oplus K_3, \\ \alpha_2 &= K_1 \oplus K_2 \oplus K_4, & \alpha_4 &= K_1 \oplus K_2 \oplus K_3 \oplus K_4. \end{aligned}$$

The coefficient matrix over $\text{GF}(2)$,

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix},$$

has full rank. The solution is direct: for $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, $\alpha_4 \oplus \alpha_j$ leaves only a single K_q on the right, and $\alpha_1 \oplus \alpha_2 \oplus \alpha_3$ gives K_1 (K_2, K_3, K_4 appear twice and cancel, K_1 three times and survives). That is:

$$\begin{aligned} K_1 &= \alpha_1 \oplus \alpha_2 \oplus \alpha_3, & K_3 &= \alpha_2 \oplus \alpha_4, \\ K_2 &= \alpha_1 \oplus \alpha_4, & K_4 &= \alpha_3 \oplus \alpha_4. \end{aligned}$$

Final formulas. Substituting the expressions of the α_j in terms of pieces and simplifying (each $W_{i,q}$ counted modulo two), we obtain the four reconstruction formulas:

$$\begin{aligned} K_1 &= W_{1,0} \oplus W_{2,0} \oplus W_{0,1} \oplus W_{2,1} \oplus W_{0,2} \oplus W_{2,2} \oplus W_{0,3} \oplus W_{1,3}, \\ K_2 &= W_{0,0} \oplus W_{2,0} \oplus W_{0,2} \oplus W_{0,3} \oplus W_{1,2} \oplus W_{2,3}, \\ K_3 &= W_{0,0} \oplus W_{1,0} \oplus W_{0,1} \oplus W_{2,1} \oplus W_{0,3} \oplus W_{2,3}, \\ K_4 &= W_{0,0} \oplus W_{1,0} \oplus W_{0,1} \oplus W_{1,1} \oplus W_{0,2} \oplus W_{1,3} \oplus W_{2,2} \oplus W_{2,3}, \end{aligned}$$

then $s = K_1 \parallel K_2 \parallel K_3 \parallel K_4$ by concatenation.

Generalization. For each of the $\binom{m}{n} = 10$ coalitions of the 3-of-5 configuration, we repeat exactly the same mechanics: the pivots change (the share used to eliminate $R^{(0)}$ and the one used to eliminate $R^{(1)}$ are not always S_0 and S_1), but the structure — two passes of randomness elimination, telescoping via the A_i chains, then a 4×4 system in the K_q — stays identical. For the other parameter sets (n, m, L) , the dimensions adapt ($n - 1$ passes of randomness elimination, a final system of $p - 1$ equations in $p - 1$ unknowns), but the method is unchanged. The implementation `xor_kurihara.py` performs this solving generically for any valid configuration.

B.5 Reconstructing a lost share: 3-of-5

This appendix complements the previous one. We assume that a share has been misplaced and that we hold the $n = 3$ shares $\{S_0, S_1, S_2\}$ to regenerate the share S_3 . The method generalizes immediately to the other coalitions and the other parameter sets; `xor_kurihara.py` implements it generically.

Overview. Reconstruction proceeds in three steps:

1. Reconstitute the fragments K_1, K_2, K_3, K_4 by the formulas of Appendix B.4.
2. Arbitrarily choose the free variable $R_4^{(1)}$ (for example to 0) and cascade through the equations to derive all the other random values.
3. Recompute the pieces $W_{3,q}$ by the direct formula.

Why the arbitrary choice works. As noted in Appendix B, the random values retain a residual degree of freedom: simultaneously replacing $R_\ell^{(t)} \mapsto R_\ell^{(t)} \oplus c$ for all (t, ℓ) leaves each piece $W_{i,q}$ unchanged. This is exactly what makes the procedure robust: whatever value we choose for $R_4^{(1)}$, the pieces $W_{3,q}$ that we compute at the end are *identical* to those of the original share, because they depend on the R only through that same symmetry which cancels out.

Step 1: reconstitute the K. The formulas of Appendix B.4 directly give:

$$\begin{aligned} K_1 &= W_{1,0} \oplus W_{2,0} \oplus W_{0,1} \oplus W_{2,1} \oplus W_{0,2} \oplus W_{2,2} \oplus W_{0,3} \oplus W_{1,3}, \\ K_2 &= W_{0,0} \oplus W_{2,0} \oplus W_{0,2} \oplus W_{0,3} \oplus W_{1,2} \oplus W_{2,3}, \\ K_3 &= W_{0,0} \oplus W_{1,0} \oplus W_{0,1} \oplus W_{2,1} \oplus W_{0,3} \oplus W_{2,3}, \\ K_4 &= W_{0,0} \oplus W_{1,0} \oplus W_{0,1} \oplus W_{1,1} \oplus W_{0,2} \oplus W_{1,3} \oplus W_{2,2} \oplus W_{2,3}. \end{aligned}$$

Step 2: cascade the random values. We set $R_4^{(1)} = 0$. The cascade exploits, at each step, an equation containing only a single unknown random value:

$$\begin{aligned} W_{2,2} &= R_2^{(0)} \oplus R_4^{(1)} && \Rightarrow R_2^{(0)} = W_{2,2}, \\ W_{1,3} &= R_3^{(0)} \oplus R_4^{(1)} \oplus K_2 && \Rightarrow R_3^{(0)} = W_{1,3} \oplus K_2, \\ W_{2,3} &= R_3^{(0)} \oplus R_0^{(1)} \oplus K_1 && \Rightarrow R_0^{(1)} = W_{2,3} \oplus R_3^{(0)} \oplus K_1, \\ W_{0,0} &= R_0^{(0)} \oplus R_0^{(1)} && \Rightarrow R_0^{(0)} = W_{0,0} \oplus R_0^{(1)}, \\ W_{0,2} &= R_2^{(0)} \oplus R_2^{(1)} \oplus K_2 && \Rightarrow R_2^{(1)} = W_{0,2} \oplus R_2^{(0)} \oplus K_2, \\ W_{1,1} &= R_1^{(0)} \oplus R_2^{(1)} && \Rightarrow R_1^{(0)} = W_{1,1} \oplus R_2^{(1)}, \\ W_{0,1} &= R_1^{(0)} \oplus R_1^{(1)} \oplus K_1 && \Rightarrow R_1^{(1)} = W_{0,1} \oplus R_1^{(0)} \oplus K_1, \\ W_{0,3} &= R_3^{(0)} \oplus R_3^{(1)} \oplus K_3 && \Rightarrow R_3^{(1)} = W_{0,3} \oplus R_3^{(0)} \oplus K_3. \end{aligned}$$

All the $R_q^{(0)}$ and $R_\ell^{(1)}$ are now known (modulo the shift c which, as we saw, vanishes in the computation of the pieces).

Step 3: recompute the pieces of the lost share. By the direct formula $W_{3,q} = R_q^{(0)} \oplus R_{(3+q) \bmod 5}^{(1)} \oplus K_{(q-3) \bmod 5}$:

$$\begin{aligned} W_{3,0} &= R_0^{(0)} \oplus R_3^{(1)} \oplus K_2, \\ W_{3,1} &= R_1^{(0)} \oplus R_4^{(1)} \oplus K_3 = R_1^{(0)} \oplus K_3 \quad (\text{since } R_4^{(1)} = 0 \text{ by choice}), \\ W_{3,2} &= R_2^{(0)} \oplus R_0^{(1)} \oplus K_4, \\ W_{3,3} &= R_3^{(0)} \oplus R_1^{(1)} \oplus K_0 = R_3^{(0)} \oplus R_1^{(1)} \quad (\text{since } K_0 = 0 \text{ by convention}). \end{aligned}$$

The share S_3 thus reconstituted is bit-for-bit identical to the original, and can replace it without modifying the other shares in circulation.

Warning. This regeneration assumes that the lost share has not been *compromised*: if one suspects that a third party has seen it, regenerating it identically leaves that third party in possession of a valid share. In that case the whole scheme must be rotated — generate a new set of random values, recompute all shares, distribute the new ones, destroy the old ones.

B.6 Why p must be prime

If p is not prime, the map $i \mapsto t \cdot i \bmod p$ is no longer a bijection for the t that share a factor with p . Concretely, for $m = 4$, $n = 3$, $p = 4$ (incorrect because not prime), consider the set $t = 2$. The randomness indices used by share i are $(2i + q) \bmod 4$ for $q = 0, 1, 2$. For $i = 0$ and $i = 2$, we have $2 \cdot 0 \equiv 0$ and $2 \cdot 2 \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$: the two shares therefore use, position by position, exactly the same indices $\{0, 1, 2\}$ for this set.

XORing $W_{0,q} \oplus W_{2,q}$, the set $t = 0$ cancels (the indices $R_q^{(0)}$ are identical for all shares, and here appear twice) *and* the set $t = 2$ cancels for the same reason. Only a single effective randomness set remains to mask the fragments, whereas two would be needed for a threshold $n = 3$. The adversary therefore reconstitutes combinations of fragments with just two shares: information leak, threshold broken.

With p prime, $\gcd(t, p) = 1$ for every $t \in \{1, \dots, p-1\}$, and the bijection $i \mapsto t \cdot i \bmod p$ guarantees that such collisions are impossible. It is precisely this property, structural to the choice of p , that makes primality indispensable to the scheme.

B.7 Automated tests

The reference implementation `xor_kurihara.py` includes a test mode which, for given parameters (n, m, L) , generates a random secret, computes the m shares, verifies reconstruction for each coalition of n shares out of m , and verifies that no sub-coalition of $n - 1$ shares can reconstruct. The results on the tested configurations:

Configuration	Coalitions OK	Safe sub-coalitions	Verdict
2-of-3, $L = 128$	3/3	—	✓
2-of-5, $L = 256$	10/10	—	✓
3-of-5, $L = 256$	10/10	5/5	✓
4-of-5, $L = 256$	5/5	5/5	✓

Underlying scheme: J. Kurihara, S. Kiyomoto, K. Fukushima, T. Tanaka, “A New (k, n) -Threshold Secret Sharing Scheme and Its Extension”, ISC 2008.

<https://eprint.iacr.org/2008/409>

Security analysis carried out by CaverneCrypto, April 2026.

References

- [1] J. Kurihara, S. Kiyomoto, K. Fukushima, T. Tanaka. *A New (k, n) -Threshold Secret Sharing Scheme and Its Extension*. ISC 2008. <https://eprint.iacr.org/2008/409>.